

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**IN-PATIENT SATISFACTION AND ITS ASSOCIATED
ELEMENTS IN NISHTAR HOSPITAL MULTAN****¹Dr. Hira Khurram, ²Dr. Umbreen Anwar, ³Dr. Fatima Altaf**¹Women Medical Officer Basic Health Unit, Ahdhian Tehsil, Muridke District Sheikhpura²WMO, Basic Health Unit, Chechian Shamas, Gujrat³Services Hospital Lahore**Abstract:**

Objective: The quality of monitoring care of the patients in the hospitals plays a vital role to know about the contentment of the patients. This work was carried out to know about the reasons of the satisfaction of the patients.

Methodology: Method which was used for the study in 2017 was cross sectional study. 476 patients from 5021 were chosen as sample. A face to face interview was carried out at discharge time in the hospitals. Talented personnel were chosen to take interviews. Pearson's Correlation was used to know about the correlation between the variables.

Results: Most of the patients about eighty-three percent were happy because they were well looked after in hospitals but one percent were not happy with the prevailing conditions. More than ninety-one percent patients were very happy after talking with physicians and to see the way of their treatment. Nourishment status can have satisfied only twenty-seven percent patients. This research did not have any attachment with the qualification and age of the patients. Both genders were the part of this study whose stay at the hospitals was eleven to fifteen days because they were more satisfied with the way treatment was provided to them from hospital staff.

Conclusions: Patients were very happy due to the way they were being cared in the hospitals. This kind of other research works are required for improving the care in the hospitals and it will bring best outcome.

Key Words: Cure, Nourishment, Treatment, Variables, Satisfy, Doctor, Physician

Corresponding author:**Dr. Hira Khurram,**

Women Medical Officer Basic Health Unit,

Ahdhian Tehsil,

Muridke District Sheikhpura

QR code

Please cite this article in press Hira Khurram et al., *In-Patient Satisfaction and Its Associated Elements in Nishtar Hospital Multan*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(05).

INTRODUCTION:

For check and balance of care carried out in the hospital it is very important to know about the contentment of the patients. It is very important to know about the satisfaction of the patients because it provides the policies and ways of providing services to the patients. To know about the services and cost provided by the hospital, satisfaction plays a vital role to judge it. Different kinds of researches have been carried out to know about the factors of satisfaction in the patients. A research carried out in Multan proved that contentment of the patients can be gained by doctors, food provided in hospitals and different kind of equipment used for the tests. There is a great rule of qualification and sex to satisfy the patients [1]. A research carried out in Pakistan proved that male physicians can satisfy more patients than the female doctors and an opposite relationship was observed between qualification and contentment. In Punjab, there was a short knowledge about the contentment of the patients present in hospitals. The main purpose of this research was to know the level of satisfaction in one hospital Therefore the aim of this study was to find out patient satisfaction and its influencing factors with care in one teaching hospital located in Multan and explore the associated factors [2]. It was the 3rd research of this kind carried out in the country. The outcome of this research will be used as the base to improve the condition of the hospitals on national level.

METHODOLOGY:

In 2017, this research was carried out on the different patients admitted in the hospital. Four hundred and seventy-six patients were selected out of five thousand and twenty-one as sample on different occasions for study. Patients were selected from different medical wards. Ethic committee gave the approval of the research. Face to face interview was carried out at the departure time of the patients by expert and skilled interviewers. Questions were preselected. The research was held according to the guiding principles of Helsinki declaration [3].

Only the willing candidates from patients were selected for the interviews. The modification satisfaction scale of Verona service in the patient complied for this study. The questions were of different kinds including the social behavior,

medical treatment, nourishment facilities, easiness and well communication between doctors and patients etc. For numerical data analysis, the use of the statistical package for the social science was carried out. And the views of patient satisfaction were divided into 20 different shades for the better improvement [4].

In each sample, the answer of each question was summed up to know about the particular trait. Very poor, poor, neither poor nor good, good and very good, these five parameters were used to search out the final contentment by using Likert scale of these parameters. Likert score provides a different quantity of the question to be answered to fall in a particular above mentioned five different traits. Percentage was used to mention the final outcome.

RESULTS:

More than thirty percent of the attendants were from twenty-one to thirty years of age and female participants were more than fifty percent. Maximum age of the participants was seventy-four years and the average age was between 23.2 to 57.6 years. Most of the patients about eighty-three percent were happy because they were well looked after in hospitals but one percent was not happy with the prevailing conditions. Both genders were the part of this study whose stay at the hospitals was 11 to 15 days. Table one is given which gives twenty different traits to provide the reasons of contentment for the patients.

More than ninety-one percent patients were very happy after talking with physicians and to see the way of their curing. Nourishment status can have satisfied only twenty-seven percent patients. Qualification and age factor do not have any relation with the contentment. Sixty-six percent patients were loyal to the hospital while sixty-five percent patients advised their friends to visit this hospital in case of any illness. Two thousand three hundred and eighty were the scores for every question. The attendants whose stay was less than 5 days in hospital were totally unhappy than the patients whose stay was longer in hospital. Hospitalization of the hospital was not good for both gender patients whose stay was greater than sixteen days. The attendants of the research whose stay was long were fed up with the condition of hospital while the hospital caring and service satisfied the patients of less stay in hospital.

Graph describing the description figure mentioned in table 1 given below

Table-I: Distribution of patient assessment in twenty main satisfaction components Nishtar Hospital Multan in 2006

S NO	Components Number of Cases =476	Very good %	Good %	Neither good nor bad %	Poor & very poor %	Mean $\pm$ SD
1	Satisfied with Duration of address finding	82	5	8	5	3.59 $\pm$ 1.01
2	Satisfied with Duration of reception	75	10	10	5	3.52 $\pm$ 1.01
3	Satisfied with reception staffs overall	84	8	2	6	3.64 $\pm$ 1.05
4	Satisfied with physician's explanation	91	6	2	1	4.07 $\pm$ 0.65
5	Satisfied with nurses communication	90	7	2	1	3.98 $\pm$ 0.65
6	Satisfied with night nurses care	81	11	2	6	3.69 $\pm$ 1.11
7	Satisfied with safety during night	80	11	3	6	3.61 $\pm$ 1.06
8	Satisfied with ward's staff	87	11	2	0	3.86 $\pm$ 0.53
9	Satisfied with comfort and equipment	33	26	38	3	2.83 $\pm$ 1.3
10	Satisfied with ward's silence	64	18	17	1	3.44 $\pm$ 0.86
11	Satisfied with hospital's cloths	54	17	19	10	3.05 $\pm$ 1.28
12	Satisfied with drug and instrument	62	13	13	12	3.13 $\pm$ 1.34
13	Satisfied with quality of beds	62	18	18	2	3.35 $\pm$ 0.57
14	Satisfied with cleanliness and facility	49	21	27	3	3.10 $\pm$ 1.09
15	Satisfied with nutrition status	27	18	45	10	2.43 $\pm$ 1.26
16	Satisfied with ward healthy	81	13	6	0	3.76 $\pm$ 0.59
17	Satisfied with treatment process	85	9	4	2	3.76 $\pm$ 0.71
18	Boring from hospitalization	37	11	34	18	2.46 $\pm$ 1.45
19	Telling their local health clinic about their future care needs	75	5	4	16	3.2 $\pm$ 1.49
20	Satisfied with over all of care	72	23	5	0	3.68 $\pm$ 0.64

DISCUSSION:

This research proved that most of the patients were satisfied with the care carried out in hospital. This research very much similar to the already work done. Patients were very happy after talking with physicians [5]. Earlier research carried out in the Iran male physicians can satisfy maximum patients than the female doctors. This happens because women patients have more trust in male physicians and female doctors have to perform a lot of duties at home one patient out of 3 was getting contentment from food items being provided [6]. This statement is close to the Annemieke. Quality of equipment, care at night times and cloths provided at night times were also checked in the research. There was not any link between the contentment and the age factor in this study [7]. Different researches carried out in contrast to that point because most of the patients of high age were easy to be satisfied. There is no exact relation of satisfaction with the early qualification, monthly payment, sex and Age. Japipaul study proved that age played no role in satisfaction of the patients [8]. The patients from fifteen to twenty-four years of age are high satisfied and this contentment level decreased with age and increased in the patients have sixty of the patients [9]. There is no relation between the complete contentment and the qualification. Ayatollahi study gave the inverse relation between study and satisfaction. The attendants whose stay was less than 5 days in hospital were totally unhappy than the patients whose stay was longer in hospital [10]. Hospitalization of the hospital was not good for both gender patients whose stay was greater than sixteen days. Women were less happy than men in short duration of admission with care of hospital staff [11]. Sex plays a vital role in the contentment of the patients because women have a lot of responsibilities at home to do and can cause low satisfaction. So, it should be policy of hospital to manage the well skilled nurses at night shift to provide the ideal care to the patients in nights [12]. Because, there is a lot of time to look after the patients at night times which can be the result of loyalty and contentment in the patients.

CONCLUSION:

Patients were very happy due to the way they were being cared in the hospitals. This kind of other research works are required for improving the care in the hospitals and it will bring best outcome.

Limitations of the study:

The hindrances which were faced during the course of study should be kept in view at the time

consequences of the study would be checked. First limitation was the method of study which was used to check the relations and the other was that only the current patient's data was gathered. The data of not admitted patients was not the part of this study. Using of other methods in the future may give better ways to understand this issue.

REFERENCES:

1. Tambuyzer, E. and C. Audenhove, Is perceived patient involvement in mental health care associated with satisfaction and empowerment? *Health Expectations*, 2015. 18(4): p. 516-526.
2. Turner, J.S., et al., Medical student use of communication elements and association with patient satisfaction: a prospective observational pilot study. *BMC medical education*, 2016. 16(1): p. 150.
3. Tsai, T. and E. Orav, Improving the Hospital Patient Experience. *Surgery*, 2015. 261(1): p. 2-8.
4. Graham, B., et al., Measuring patient satisfaction in orthopaedic surgery. *JBJS*, 2015. 97(1): p. 80-84.
5. Goodman, D., et al., Explanation and elaboration of the SQUIRE (Standards for Quality Improvement Reporting Excellence) Guidelines, V. 2.0: examples of SQUIRE elements in the healthcare improvement literature. *BMJ Qual Saf*, 2016. 25(12): p. e7-e7.
6. Aronis, K.N., et al., Health literacy and atrial fibrillation: relevance and future directions for patient-centred care. *European cardiology*, 2017. 12(1): p. 52.
7. Alfadda, S.A., et al., Two-Implant-Supported Mandibular Overdentures: Do Clinical Denture Quality and Inter-Implant Distance Affect Patient Satisfaction? *International Journal of Prosthodontics*, 2017. 30(6).
8. Gemmiti, M., et al., Pediatric Consultations: Negative-Word Use and Parent Satisfaction. *Journal of pediatric psychology*, 2017. 42(10): p. 1165-1174.
9. Pettit, K.E., et al., Effect of an Educational Intervention on Medical Student Scripting and Patient Satisfaction: A Randomized Trial. *Western Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 2018. 19(3): p. 585.
10. Banka, G., et al., Improving patient satisfaction through physician education, feedback, and incentives. *Journal of hospital medicine*, 2015. 10(8): p. 497-502.
11. Berkowitz, B., The patient experience and patient satisfaction: Measurement of a complex dynamic. *The Online Journal of Issues in Nursing*, 2016. 21(1).
12. Smith, M.J. and T.J. Choma, Patient satisfaction in musculoskeletal medicine. *Current reviews in musculoskeletal medicine*, 2017. 10(2): p. 207-211.